

THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The concept of "information and communication competence" can be evaluated from different points of view, both as a component of professional competence and as a component of an individual's information culture.*

Keywords: *Information and communication competence, information technology, professional activity.*

The list of significant signs includes knowledge of the basics of Information Technology, the use of a computer as a necessary technical tool, the expression of the active social position and motivation of the subjects of the educational space, the totality of knowledge, skills and qualifications related to the search, analysis and use of information. Typically, when researching specific competency formation problems, three levels of information - communicative competence acquisition are distinguished:

-base (base) - at this level, the base knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for computer literacy are formed; the minimum use of IT in the organization of professional activities (acquisition of common methods of creating, editing, storing, copying and copying information in electronic form, presentation of information through the means of presentation Technologies, acquisition of information search skills in the internet network and choosing a method (or a combination of these) of interaction in the network that is increasingly consistent with the nature of the problem and allows it to be solved by increasingly optimal methods;

-technological (at this level, ICT becomes an instrument of practical activity (assessment of the potential of internet resources, their interactivity and informativeness from a targeted point of view; analysis of global computer network resources and software tools taking into account the main technological, economic, ergonomic and technical requirements; analysis of the quality, tools and forms of providing software-technological and information;

-to be qualified to create new tools for professional activities at the practical (professional) level and to use them effectively in educational processes.

- basic level-invariant of the necessary knowledge, qualifications and skills to achieve educational goals in IT tools based on the tasks of the educator;

- pedagogical (psychological-pedagogical, methodological, creative) level-the development of electronic means corresponding to the goals of professional activity, the use of IT tools in solving tasks to ensure the spiritual maturation of the individual can be distinguished.

The effective passage of educational processes and the provision of expected results from it assumes that certain requirements and conditions must be followed in this process. Strict adherence to the following conditions ensures the effectiveness of the process of using information and communication technologies when conducting events:

- setting a clear goal, which is aimed at organizing each educational event;

- predicting the achievable result;

-theoretical justification of the goals, objectives and results of Education;

- creation of a project for the use of modern technologies in the organization of professional

activities;

- mobilizing technologies that are planned to use to guarantee the result;
 - construction of professional activities on the basis of an intensive basis, that is, maximum scientific accuracy, effective result with low resource consumption;
 - transform the educational process into a manageable process;
 - special attention to the use of effective forms, methods and tools in the educational process;
 - to achieve the decision-making of creative cooperation between educators and educators in the educational process;
 - increase the activity of educators;
 - analysis of the effectiveness in achieving the educational goal, expert assessment.
 - The use of modern information technologies in the educational process leads to an increase in the effectiveness of educational methods, a change in the work activity of teachers, improvement of their methods of work, structural changes in pedagogical systems. This puts specific tasks in the organization and management of informatization of the educational institution.
 - Effective organization of the educational process on the basis of modern information technologies:
 - integration of educators, computer programmers, relevant specialists into the development team of educational materials;
 - the distribution of tasks between them;
 - it is necessary to improve the organization of the educational institution and monitor the effectiveness of this activity.
 - when setting a goal for organizing training on the basis of modern information technologies, the following factors should initially be identified:
 - the purpose of using modern information and communication technologies;
 - technologies used to achieve the purpose of the event;
 - methods of providing information materials;
 - training methods;
 - types of discussion assignments to be presented;
 - ways to organize debates and debates;
- All this is carried out jointly by educators and technology specialists-who are responsible for training training.

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